

Work-related attitudes of employees in the emerging ITES-BPO sector of Sri Lanka

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Purpose- To explore work-related attitudes of ITES-BPO employees.

Design/methodology/approach- There are 25 firms operating in Sri Lanka that fall into the category of ITES-BPO; a random sample of 117 employees from these 25 firms responded to the survey.

Findings- The findings suggest that tenure has a significant effect on task autonomy and marital status has a significant effect on working hours.

Originality/value- A research exploring work-related attitudes of ITES-BPO employees towards their work and work environment in a South Asian country that is considered as active and promising destination for such services could provide practitioners with key information that could enable them to make informed managerial decisions.

Keywords: HRM, Outsourcing, Work-related attitudes, Sri Lanka.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

Information technology (IT) enabled business process outsourcing (ITES-BPO) services are the services that can be outsourced using the powers of IT. As much of the studies have been carried out to understand the impact of BPO in terms of the economy, and workforce on client western countries (Borman, 2006) and consequently, Asian developing countries, where ITES-BPO industry is evolving rapidly, make for an interesting area of study. Though there is abundance of literature in the Indian context on workforce issues in this sector, there is an absence in literature from the other parts of Asia. In the Sri Lankan context workforce issues in ITES-BPO sector are under-researched areas.

In Sri Lanka, ITES-BPO industry offers a type of jobs not existed in the country before and offers extensive opportunities as well as challenges for people management. The growth of this industry has created expectations about its potential for job creation due to its people-intensive nature. However, people-intensive nature of this industry also poses challenges in attracting and retaining suitable personnel (Barrick and Zimmerman, 2009; Budhwar *et al.*,

2006a). On one hand, literature suggests that firms involved in outsourced work generally lack organizational resources that underpin the operation of an internal labour market and provision of sustainable long-term employment relationships (Walsh and Deery, 2006). On the other, literature suggests that firms involved in outsourced work generally engage in tighter forms of supervision and labour control to maximize short-term output (Rees and Fielder, 1992; Walsh and Deery, 2006). In Sri Lanka, the average length of employment with a single firm for an IT worker is three years. The employee turnover rate in IT sector is 9.7 per cent in the year 2004 (Sri Lanka ICT Association, 2005). Therefore, when capturing and capitalizing on individual capabilities, it is important to understand whether ITES-BPO employees' demographic characteristics influence their perceptions towards employment characteristics of the industry. Though economic globalisation with outsourcing business environment impacts on work and employment, this is an area that has been underscored by researchers.

The research question posed for the study was: How do ITES-BPO employees' work-related attitudes differ by demographic characteristics of gender, marital status, the level of education, and tenure? The study explored ITES-BPO employees' work-related attitudes in terms of six job-related factors, namely, task autonomy, task variety, uncertainty, work pressure, workload, and working hours and seven work-related outcomes, namely, satisfaction with pay, promotion, training, and job security, commitment, work exhaustion, and intention to leave.

It is expected that the findings of this study will contribute to the literature on Asian ITES-BPO industry. The evidence suggests that work-related attitudes vary by occupational group (Lim and Teo, 1998; Sengupta *et al.*, 2009), gender (Arun and Arun, 2002; Lim and Teo, 1997), tenure (Lee and Wilbur, 1985; Rogers, 1991) and the level of education (Rogers, 1991). However, most of the studies that have been conducted on outsourced work environment controlled for demographic characteristics such as age, gender, and the level of education (Grebner *et al.*, 2003; Walsh and Deery, 2006). Hence, there appears to be paucity of direct empirical data on the influence of demographic characteristics on employee perceptions towards ITES-BPO work and work environment, especially in non-western cultures. Considering the costs associated with replacing employees, it makes sense for organizations to invest in

programmes designed to retain employees. One such retention programme would be to identify work-related attitudes of employees and develop strategies to enhance work and work environment. Hence, it is expected that the study would provide valuable information not only to academic community but also to practitioners that would enable them to make informed managerial decisions in Sri Lanka. Consistent with the objective, the rest of the paper describes briefly the Sri Lankan context related to the study and reviews the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on managerial implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Sri Lankan context

When considering the specific information on ITES-BPO workforce in the country, LIRNEasia (2006) has conducted a study called "Baseline sector analysis of the BPO industry in Sri Lanka". This is the only available study to date that analysed this important sector of the country. LIRNEasia (2006) defined BPO receiver as "the act of outsourcing to a third party the responsibility of running a business process that would otherwise be conducted internally. The receiver of the outsourced process administers the process based on a defined and measurable performance matrix. It is also an independent legal entity maintaining its own accounting systems" (p4). LIRNEasia (2006) identified 25 ITES-BPO firms operating in Sri Lanka that come under the above definition in their study. The total number of employment in these firms are slightly higher than 4000 and employment is expected to increase by around 30 per cent during 2006-2007 due to the expansions of existing firms and new entrants. The median workforce size of the firms is 62. Over half (59%) the persons employed in these firms are between the ages of 18-24. 51 per cent of the employees have an Advanced Level certificate as their main academic qualification while 15 percent of the workforce comprise of graduates. Flexible employment contracts are extremely rare in the industry as there are enough personnel available to work full-time. Although employment prospects are opening up in the sector, there are difficulties in attracting and retaining suitable personnel (LIRNEasia, 2006; Sri Lanka ICT Association, 2007).

As LIRNEasia (2006) has not polled employees' work-related attitudes, available data does not allow specific conclusions for high employee turnover rate in the industry. In the above context, there is a need to better understand ITES-BPO employees and their work and work environment.

Theoretical background

Work and work environment of outsourcing organizations

The specific literature on work and work environment of outsourcing and contracting organisations identify these represent a new form of work organization, which is often designed "from scratch" (Grebner *et al.*, 2003). Hence, some researchers suggest that these organizations might offer unique opportunities to design jobs according to established principles of job design that enhance productivity (Grebner *et al.*, 2003; Parker and Wall, 1998). However, researchers argue that, typically, when new jobs are designed, such principles tend not to play a major role (Clegg *et al.*, 1997) and work is designed around technical solutions or existing organizational principles, which may imply unfavourable working conditions for employees (Parker and Wall, 1998). This seems to apply to ITES-BPOs as well, as employees in these firms also predominantly carry out tasks that are rather specialized and often simplified (Grebner *et al.*, 2003; Taylor *et al.*, 2002). Organizations with high degree of structural division of labour can maintain personnel costs low as, on one hand, simplified tasks do not require specialized personnel and, on the other, simplified tasks require a relatively short period of vocational training (Grebner *et al.*, 2003).

However, the downside of such jobs comes along with routine work, low task complexity, and consequential low utilization of qualification (knowledge, skills, and abilities) (Grebner *et al.*, 2003). Broadly, literature on work environment of outsourcing and contracting organisations identify two common features of such organizations (Budhwar *et al.*, 2006b). First, work in outsourcing environment is highly monitored and controlled by the management. Second, these organizations consist of semi-professional empowered workers who work in a positive work environment. These empowered workers customize work to the needs of customers and are

more productive than routine workers (Batt and Appelbaum, 1995). Hence, work environment is bureaucratic but has elements associated with professional or knowledge-intensive settings appropriate to the customisation of products and services. This is because, management has to adopt a form of organization which reconciles the two conflicting principles, i.e. the standardization of processes and products aimed at lowering unit costs through scale and transaction economies and customisation aimed at generating revenue by focusing on individual customer requirements (Frenkel *et al.*, 1999).

Consequently, employees working in outsourcing environment face a mixture of control and commitment strategies; the work environment is highly controlled and performance is closely monitored and strictly measured against targets though employees are encouraged to take responsibility for both their team and their own performance (Budhwar *et al.*, 2006b). In the above context, ITES-BPO employees' work-related attitudes towards six job-related factors will be investigated in this study, namely, task autonomy, task variety, uncertainty, work pressure, workload, and working hours.

Further, literature identifies that outsourcing work environment leads to emotional exhaustion, less affective commitment, more resigned attitude towards the job, and higher intention to quit (e.g. Bakker *et al.*, 2003; Grebner *et al.*, 2003; Holman *et al.*, 2002; Lewig and Dollard, 2003; Messersmith, 2007; Niederman *et al.*, 2007; Slaughter *et al.*, 2007; Witt *et al.*, 2004). In the Sri Lankan context, LIRNEasia (2006) suggests that employees quit jobs due to working time and work-life balance related issues. This is because the clients of ITES-BPOs of Sri Lanka are in the Western world. Consequently, many ITES-BPOs operate during unconventional working hours to provide real time services to different time zones (LIRNEasia, 2006). In the above context, ITES-BPO employees' work-related attitudes towards seven work-related outcomes will also be investigated in this study, namely, satisfaction with pay, promotion, training, and job security, commitment, work exhaustion, and intention to leave. The variables investigated in this study are shown in Table I.

TABLE I ABOUT HERE

Differences in employee work-related attitudes by demographic characteristics and hypotheses

Organizations in a given industry tend to take on similar norms and practices, resulting in a subset of work experiences that can be observed across various organizational contexts in a particular industry. However, evidence suggests that an individual's attitudes could differ in terms of demographic characteristics themselves (e.g., Guimaraes and Igbaria, 1992; Kuo and Chen, 2004). Though research in organizational behaviour and psychology provide solid foundations upon which to hypothesise relationships between demographic characteristics and work-related attitudes of employees (Johnson *et al.*, 2007), there is dearth of empirical research that addresses differences in work-related attitudes of ITES-BPO employees by their demographic characteristics. Therefore, though numerous studies addressed work-related attitudes, much less is known about the influence of demographic characteristics on work-related attitudes of ITES-BPO employees.

Job tenure is the length of time an individual has worked in a specific position in an organization and it can make significant variations in an individual's work-related attitudes (Guimaraes and Igbaria, 1992; Lim and Teo, 1998). When an individual has been on the job for a long time, his/her investments in the job and organization may be greater than someone who has been on the job for a short period (Lim and Teo, 1998); this could influence an individual's intention to leave the organization, job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Lim and Teo, 1998). Hence, the number of years spent in an organization is an age-related variable which can make significant variations in work-related attitudes. For this study, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 1: ITES-BPO employees' work-related attitudes will significantly vary by tenure where employees with more years of tenure will have more positive attitudes than otherwise.

A number of research studies found that work-related attitudes could differ by the level of education (Guimaraes and Igbaria, 1992; Lee and Wilbur, 1985; Rogers, 1991). The level of

education influences a person's work-related attitudes, presumably because an individual expects that rewards and responsibilities will change as the level of education increases (Churchill *et al.*, 1979). Further, Bilic (1998) found that individuals with higher level of education seemed to be more concerned with productivity and have few negative feelings towards their work. For this study, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 2: ITES-BPO employees' work-related attitudes will significantly vary by the level of education where employees with high level of education will have more positive attitudes than otherwise.

A considerable amount of literature has focused on differences between men and women in terms of their work-related attitudes. Several studies found that women have been marginalized in promotion, salary raises, assignments to challenging tasks, and access to authority (Guimaraes and Igbaria, 1992; Sumner and Niederman, 2004). However, there may be lack of gender differences in employee attitudes towards training if both males and females are subjected to common training experience and socialization process (Lim and Teo 1998). Employee turnover rate has been accepted as an important indicator of the quality of experience and hospitable climate for women in organizations. Wardell *et al.*, (2005) found that females are nearly three times as likely as their male counterparts to leave IT workforce. It is, therefore, critical to focus on the extent to which women who have successfully entered the field intend to leave the industry. For this study, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 3: ITES-BPO employees' work-related attitudes will significantly vary by gender where male employees will have more positive attitudes than otherwise.

Evidence suggests that social roles may influence what a person wants from a job (Scandura and Lankau, 1997). While work-family balance plays an important role in influencing women's career decisions, research evidence suggests that work-related factors also play an important role in contributing to women's relatively high turnover rate (Sumner and Niederman, 2004). For this study, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 4: ITES-BPO employees' work-related attitudes will significantly vary by marital status where married employees will have more positive attitudes than otherwise.

It is expected that the results of this study would lead to determine the variables that influence work-related attitudes of ITES-BPO employees to better understand and address issues in the industry thereby allowing suitable updates to be made to prevent the deterioration of working conditions in these firms.

Methodology

Population and sample

LIRNEasia (2006) identified that there are 25 ITES-BPO firms operating in Sri Lanka by the end of September 2006. These 25 firms were considered as the population frame for this study. It was decided to survey all the 25 firms. These BPO firms provide services in customer care, financial, medical, and legal services. Table II shows the characteristics of the firms.

TABLE II ABOUT HERE

Two hundred questionnaires were distributed among a random sample of ITES-BPO employees from the 25 firms by the end of 2007. In total, 121 respondents voluntarily responded within four weeks of initial questionnaire distribution. A total of 117 usable responses resulted in 59 percent usable response rate ($117/200 * 100 = 0.585$). The characteristics of employee respondents are also shown in Table II. The age categorization revealed that all respondents are below 30 years of age. This may be due to the nature of Sri Lankan ITES-BPO industry, which is young. Fifty six percent of the sample reported General Certificate in Education (Advanced Level) as their highest level of education while 44 percent reported diploma or degree as their highest level of education. When it comes to tenure in the present workplace, 62 per cent reported less than three years of tenure in the present workplace while 38 percent

reported more than three years of tenure in the present work place. LIRNEasia (2006) is the only reliable source available by the time of this study that provided population characteristics of 25 ITES-BPO firms operating in Sri Lanka and their employees. Our study was conducted about one year after LIRNEasia's (2006) study on the same 25 ITES-BPO firms (total population). Overall, we observed that the sample characteristics of our study do not show considerable deviation from the population characteristics of ITES-BPOs depicted in the study of LIRNEasia (2006).

Measures and methods of data analysis

The self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection. Respondents were asked to indicate their attitudes to their work regime at the ITES-BPO in which they were currently employed. In addition, respondents provided information on their perceptions of the extent to which skills and knowledge used by them in their current workplace are needed in non-BPO work organisations of the country. With the exception of the demographic characteristics, participants responded to items on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 'strongly disagree' = 1 to 'strongly agree' = 5. The measures used for the study are shown in Appendix I. The inter-item correlation test was conducted; standardized Cronbach's alpha reliabilities for each of the constructs were above the customary reference point of 0.70. Respondents' demographic characteristics were recoded into two levels (eg: male 0, female 1). Independent sample t-test was conducted to identify differences by demographic variables.

Results and managerial implications

The results of descriptive analysis and t-test for mean comparisons by demographic characteristics are presented in Table III. The results of t-test reveal that the differences in mean values are significant for task autonomy by tenure ($p < 0.05$), and working hours by marital status ($p < 0.01$). Employees with more than three years of work experience feel there are considerable opportunities for independence and freedom in doing their work than employees with less than three years of work experience. Hence H1 is partially supported. H2 and H3 are not supported

in our study. Married employees show more resentment towards working hours than unmarried employees. Hence H4 is partially supported. Tenure correlates significantly with task autonomy ($p < 0.05$) while marital status correlates significantly with working hours ($p < 0.01$).

TABLE III ABOUT HERE

The results suggest that marital status has a significant effect on working hours. The geographical distance between Western client locations and Sri Lanka create a special challenge on employees. The 13-hour time difference between Sri Lanka and Vancouver, for example, has been useful as work sent to Sri Lanka at the end of the day from Vancouver is often completed when Canadian employees return to work the following morning. However, the erratic working hours make normal socialization difficult, leading to alienation and identity crisis. Further, unconventional working hours especially “grave-yard” shifts are perceived unfavourably and reported to be a problem for employees who are married or have families. Though many firms provide transport facilities for employees during non-traditional work times— at least one way “from office when they work late” or “when they have to come early to work”— married employees may prefer to work on traditional working hours. Further, findings suggest that tenure has a significant main effect to task autonomy. Task autonomy refers to the perception of employees with regard to freedom and flexibility provided to them in terms of ‘how’ they serve customers and ‘what’ they do in serving them, and also in relation to the personal initiative allowed to be exercised while performing their duties (see Hackman and Oldham, 1976). The findings imply that longer service translates into opportunities for independence and freedom in doing their work.

The organizational hierarchy of ITES-BPO firms is extremely flat having about two layers in the organizational hierarchy; opportunities available for promotion are few and far between. The findings of the study imply that employees are well aware of this situation as perceived promotional opportunities are not influenced by any of the demographic characteristics explored

in this study. To compensate the lack of promotional opportunities, firms offer attractive remuneration packages. Though in US Dollar terms cost of labour is considerably low with compared to other countries in the region, in Sri Lankan Rupee terms ITES-BPO employees are paid relatively high salaries in the national context. With regard to training, training in ITES-BPOs includes induction and continuous and regular training to employees for providing quality service. The findings led to suggest that all employees irrespective of their gender, the level of education, marital status and tenure are subject to similar training experience. This common training experience may account for the lack of differences by demographic characteristics. With the increased tenure in the workplace employees have adjusted their expectations and accepted the fact that promotion opportunities are limited. Additionally, findings suggest that longer tenure increases an individual's investment in the employing organization and increases autonomy which accumulate with time as organizations usually reward long-term membership. Therefore, mean values for intention to leave imply that, overall, employees have low intention to leave. In this regard, employee perceptions suggest that their skills are not highly transferable across different firms and even different industries belong to non-BPOs of the country. This may also influence them to exhibit loyalty to their organizations.

The literature reviewed earlier identifies outsourcing organisations represent a new form of work organization. As ITES-BPO work continues to be outsourced, challenges facing the ITES-BPO worker persist. All most all previous research studies conducted on work-related factors in outsourcing organisations attempted to identify the most important factors that influence employee perceptions towards organizational commitment, intentions to quit, etc. controlling for demographic characteristics. Specifically, there appears to be paucity of direct empirical data on differences in work-related attitudes of ITES-BPO employees in terms of demographic characteristics. Therefore, the paper contributed to the literature by bringing some much-needed diversity to the topic of how demographic characteristics make variations in work-related attitudes of ITES-BPO employees in Sri Lanka. When self-reports accurately reflect an individual's work-related attitudes and as long as the profile of individuals is known along with

their work-related attitudes, identifying strategies to improve the work environment of ITES-BPOs would not be difficult.

The growth of the Sri Lankan ITES-BPO industry has been accompanied by policy level interventions and national campaigns and programmes under a comprehensive framework. Sri Lankan organizations increasingly realize the need of operating in a global market and the need of developing global strategies to locate them in a globally competitive environment. In competitively-challenged sectors, like ITES-BPO, firms rely heavily on their human resource. The way ITES-BPO firms manage their personnel should essentially manifested in their human resource management (HRM) practices. Overall, when looking ahead to the results as its implications for the management of organizations in order to make better use of the opportunities that motivated and committed employees could contribute to an organization, results provide better understanding of the differences that demographic characteristics could make in influencing work-related attitudes of ITES-BPO employees. Therefore, the findings imply the need of introducing adjustments and adaptations to people management strategies and practices by taking into account any discrepancies that exist according to demographic characteristics of employees.

Limitations and further research

This study was designed as a cross-sectional study employing quantitative methodology with a sample confined to ITES-BPO employees in Sri Lanka. On the strong side of our study is the fact that we have covered the whole population of ITES-BPO firms operating in the country and selected a random sample of employees who comprise them. Some limitations of this study, however, should be acknowledged. The study exclusively used self-reports of employees to poll their work-related attitudes. As we were unable to find similar studies conducted in the Western or Asian context, we are unable to see how far the findings of this study do/do not resemble the findings of previous studies. When considering some possible directions for future research, it would be fascinating to explore the ways in which demographic characteristics interact with each other. Further, future studies could investigate other features- like social and cultural

context within organizations and general society to understand how these features get factored in. Some of the ITES-BPO firms have separate HRM department while some do not have such. Therefore, one could assume that employees would have been exposed to different HRM practices. As the effect of outsourcing on employees' attitudes could not easily be disentangled from the effects of different HRM practices prevail in their firms, future studies could also explore HRM practices used by these firms. Last but not least, future studies could extend findings to cross-cultural research. The ways in which demographic characteristics influence work-related attitudes of Sri Lankan employees could be tested against other Asian countries that involved in ITES-BPO work.

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Tables

Table I: Work-related attitudes

Job-related factors

- Task autonomy
- Task variety
- Uncertainty
- Work pressure
- Workload
- Working hours

Work-related outcomes

- Satisfaction with pay
- Satisfaction with promotion
- Satisfaction with training
- Satisfaction with job security
- Organizational commitment
- Work exhaustion
- Intention to leave

Table II. Characteristics of the firms and employee sample

Characteristics of the firms and the selection of employee sample	Total firms (N=25) %		Employee sample (N=117) %	
Service region:			Age:	
USA	50	50	25 years or less	36
UK and Europe	42	43	26 to 30 years	64
Asia Pacific	8	7	Gender:	
			Female	54
Years of operation:			Male	46
Less than 3 years	38	66	Marital status:	
3 or more years	62	34	Married	33
			Unmarried	67
Workforce:			The highest level of education:	
300 or less	92	49	A/L or below	56
More than 300	8	51	Diploma/Degree	44
Existence of HR department/unit:			Tenure in present workplace:	
Yes	71	82	Less than 3 years	62
No	29	18	3 or more years	38
			Total years of work experience:	
			Less than 5 years	61
			5 years or more	39

Table III. t-test for mean comparisons by gender, tenure in the present workplace, the highest level of education and marital status

	Demographic characteristics											
	Gender			Tenure			Education			Marital status		
	Male	Female	Sig (2-tailed)	Less than 3	3 or more	Sig (2-tailed)	Diploma/ Degree	A/L or below	Sig (2-tailed)	Unmarried	Married	Sig (2-tailed)
Working hours	3.88	3.76	0.509	3.79	3.86	0.704	3.81	3.82	0.952	3.62	4.23	0.002**
Task autonomy	3.27	3.03	0.270	2.98	3.40	0.069*	3.06	3.25	0.400	3.08	3.28	0.385
Task variety	3.20	3.33	0.563	3.20	3.37	0.460	3.08	3.23	0.732	3.31	3.21	0.665
Uncertainty	3.48	3.34	0.556	3.30	3.57	0.236	3.33	3.50	0.473	3.74	3.82	0.409
Work pressure	2.90	3.19	0.151	3.12	2.95	0.403	3.03	3.09	0.742	3.10	2.97	0.540
Workload	2.94	2.68	0.240	2.75	2.88	0.544	2.72	2.84	0.732	2.82	2.77	0.826
Pay satisfaction	3.74	3.76	0.919	3.77	3.71	0.756	3.90	3.85	0.893	3.77	3.72	0.817
Promotion	2.55	2.52	0.892	2.59	2.44	0.522	2.64	2.40	0.299	2.60	2.41	0.435
Job security	3.70	3.95	0.233	3.91	3.72	0.337	3.81	3.86	0.812	3.94	3.64	0.181
Training	3.64	3.55	0.685	3.72	3.40	0.167	3.73	3.42	0.167	3.49	3.84	0.166
Commitment	3.67	3.66	0.932	3.65	3.68	0.792	3.61	3.75	0.535	3.76	3.51	0.286
Work exhaustion	3.25	3.09	0.455	3.12	3.24	0.595	3.23	2.09	0.541	3.17	3.18	0.956
Intention to leave	3.62	3.68	0.812	3.59	3.75	0.486	3.78	3.50	0.200	2.34	2.33	0.623
Skills and knowledge used in current job are needed in non-BPOs	2.87	2.84	0.905	2.75	3.02	0.273	2.76	2.96	0.430	2.91	2.74	0.516

Note

* p<0.05; **p<0.01

For any of the variable, normality distribution was not violated in running the t-test

Values of the standard deviation ranged between 0.47 (lowest) to 1.11 (highest).

Appendix I: Variables

Variable	Source	Sample items
Task autonomy	Thatcher et al. (2002)	Job gives me considerable opportunity for independence and freedom in how I do the work
Task variety	Thatcher et al. (2002)	Job requires me to use a number of complex or high-level skills
Uncertainty	Zapf <i>et al.</i> (2003)	How often do you get contradictory orders?
Work pressure	Caplan <i>et al.</i> (1975)	My job requires me to work very fast
Perceived workload	Kirmeyer and Dougherty (1988)	I feel that the number of requests, problems, or complaints I deal with is more than expected
Working hours	Developed for this study	I am uncomfortable with my working hours
Pay satisfaction	Cammann <i>et al.</i> (1983)	I am very happy with the amount of money I make
Perceived promotional opportunities	Price and Mueller (1986)	promotional opportunities are widely available
Job security	Oldham <i>et al.</i> (1986)	I am confident that I will be able to work for [the organization] as long as I wish
Training	Caplan <i>et al.</i> (1975)	I have sufficient training to deal with the requirements of my job
Commitment	Porter et al. (1974)	I am willing to put in a great deal of effort beyond that normally required in order to help [the organization] be successful
Work exhaustion	Wharton (1993)	I feel used up at the end of the work day
Voluntarily turnover	Cammann <i>et al.</i> (1983)	I often think about quitting
Skills and knowledge used in the current workplace are needed in non-BPOs	Developed for this study	The skills and knowledge used in my job are needed in non-BPO workplaces of the country